

CLITORIA TERNATEA (BUTTERFLY PEA): A REVIEW ON ITS PHYTOCHEMISTRY AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

Clitoria ternatea, also known as butterfly pea is a medicinal plant widely recognized for its rich phytochemical composition and diverse biological activities. Numerous studies have identified the presence of bioactive compounds most of the unique secondary metabolites and their analogues identified in plants including anthocyanins, flavonoids, phenolic acids, tannins, and alkaloids, which contribute to its pharmacological properties (Mukherjee et al., 2008; Oguis et al., 2019). These compounds exhibit vital antioxidant protection such as anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and neuroprotective effects. In this past years Clitoria ternatea has been getting attention for its potential benefits in the field of cosmetic science. Furthermore, its anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activities promote a healthy scalp environment, which is essential for optimal hair growth (Jeyaraj et al., 2021). This review aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the phytochemistry and biological activities of Clitoria ternatea, and its potential applications in health. Despite of having positive effects most existing research relies on in vitro or small-scale sample groups that leaves a significant gap in the literature regarding the efficacy of the combined formulation on a clinical level.

KEYWORD: Clitoria ternatea (butterfly pea), phytochemistry and biological activities.

1. INTRODUCTION

Clitoria ternatea is a perennial herbaceous plant belonging to the Fabaceae family and is widely distributed across tropical and subtropical regions. One of the most significant findings is the presence of anthocyanins, particularly ternatins, which are responsible for the plant's vibrant blue coloration which have been traditionally used as natural dyes, food colorants, and herbal remedies. This antioxidant activity is significant because oxidative stress is closely associated with the development of chronic conditions such as cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and neurodegenerative disorders (Marpaung et al., 2022). In addition, bioactive peptides isolated from the plant have also been shown to enhance antioxidant defenses, further supporting its potential use in functional foods and nutraceutical applications (Shen et al., 2024). In traditional systems of medicine such as Ayurveda, the plant has been utilized for its memory-enhancing,

anxiolytic, and anti-stress properties (Mukherjee et al., 2008) and also these compounds are known for their strong antioxidant activity, which plays a crucial role in neutralizing free radicals and reducing oxidative stress (Lakshmi et al., 2014) lastly the antioxidant properties of Clitoria ternatea help counteract these effects by protecting hair follicles from oxidative damage, thereby supporting healthy hair growth (Oguis et al., 2019).

With the growing demand for natural and plant-based products, the plant is rich in bioactive compounds that are responsible for its pharmacological activities, the chemical composition and biological properties of Clitoria ternatea highlights its potential for use in both medical and cosmetic fields. Overall, current research findings support the viability of Clitoria ternatea as a natural therapeutic agent.

1.1 Botanical and taxonomic description of *Clitoria ternatea*

Clitoria ternatea is a perennial, herbaceous climbing plant widely known as butterfly pea. It belongs to the family Fabaceae which is the legume or pea family and sub family of Faboideae. The plant is valued for its striking blue flowers and its wide range of traditional medicinal and culinary uses. It classified as plantae this plant is a fast growing, twining herbaceous vine that can reach up to 3-5 meters in length it has slender, cylindrical stems that are slightly pubescent when young and become woodier with age (Jeyaraj *et al.*, 2021) *Clitoria ternatea* exhibits compound, pinnate leaves and the most significant feature is its flowers. They are solitary, axillary and showy typically deep blue in color although there are also white and violet exist. The flower is papilionaceous (butterfly-shaped), a characteristic feature of the Fabaceae family. It has a large standard petal, two wing petals, and two fused keel petals (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2019). The flowers are bisexual and zygomorphic, meaning they have bilateral symmetry.

The fruit of *Clitoria ternatea* is a flattened, linear pod (legume) that is 5–10 cm long, containing several small, kidney-shaped seeds. When mature, the pods turn brown and dehisce to release the seeds. The root system is taproot-based, allowing the plant to adapt well to different soil conditions, particularly well-drained sandy or loamy soils (Jeyaraj *et al.*, 2021). *Clitoria ternatea* is native to tropical Asia but is now widely distributed in tropical and subtropical regions across the world. It thrives in warm climates, full sunlight, and moderate rainfall conditions. The plant is commonly found in gardens, fences, grasslands, and disturbed areas.

2. METHODOLOGY

This review employed a descriptive research design, specifically a narrative review approach. The aim was to provide an overview and conceptual understanding of existing literature on *Clitoria ternatea*, with particular emphasis on identifying its phytochemical constituents and summarizing their associated biological activities.

Only studies published in English were included due to accessibility and availability of resources. The data used in this review were obtained exclusively from secondary sources, particularly peer-reviewed journal articles published between 2000 and 2025. These articles were carefully selected based on their relevance to the phytochemical profile and biological activities of *Clitoria ternatea*.

The collected literature was systematically examined and synthesized to identify recurring findings, proposed mechanisms of action, and key therapeutic properties associated with the plant's bioactive compounds. In addition, this review highlights existing gaps, inconsistencies, and areas requiring further investigation within the current body of knowledge. Through this approach, the study aims to consolidate current scientific

evidence and provide a comprehensive understanding of the phytochemical and pharmacological significance of *Clitoria ternatea*.

3. Phytochemistry of *Clitoria ternatea*

FLOWERS

The benefits of *C. ternatea* have been recognized since ancient times, believed to be a natural cure for many diseases, and also used as a natural food additive. Besides the phytochemical compounds, the nutritional composition of *C. ternatea* flowers has been identified and reported by (Neda *et al.*, 2013)

Various phenolic compounds contained in the plant are responsible for the beneficial effects, especially the petals of the flower. *C. ternatea* contains many bioactive compounds, such as alkaloids, tannins, glycosides, resins, steroids, saponins, flavonoids, and phenols. Another study also stated that maltosylated flavanol glycosides were isolated from the flower petals.

(Mukherjee 2008) and (Kazuma *et al.*, 2003) reported that the phenolics compounds found in the flowers of *C. ternatea* are mainly ternatin anthocyanins and various flavanol glycosides of kaempferol, rutin, quercetin, and myricetin, which are isolated in a hydrophilic extract. Meanwhile, some fatty acids (palmitic acid, stearic acids, petroselinic acid, linoleic acid, arachidic acid, behenic acid, and phytanic acid), various phytosterols such as campesterol, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, and sitostanol, and tocopherols such as α -tocopherol and γ -tocopherol are also identified in a lipophilic.

LEAVES

The leaves of *Clitoria ternatea* (Butterfly Pea) are rich in phytochemicals, including flavonoids (kaempferol, quercetin), phenols, alkaloids, terpenoids (taraxerol, taraxerone), anthocyanins, and tannins (Morita *et al.* 2001) These bioactive compounds provide the leaves with significant antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties, making them valuable in herbal medicine. From ethanolic extracts of leaves, clitorin and kaempferol have been isolated. Recent phytochemical investigations highlight the abundance of flavonoids, such as kaempferol and quercetin, in the leaves, which contribute to their potent antimicrobial and neuroprotective properties (Abubakar *et al.*, 2025). Ethanolic leaf extracts have shown significant hypoglycemic effects, effectively lowering blood glucose and insulin levels in diabetic models (Khateib *et al.*, 2025)

The roots of *C. ternatea* were traditionally used as a brain tonic to improve memory. This raises the possibility of using the roots extract as a cholinesterase inhibitor in treating Alzheimer's disease symptoms according to (Nurul Zawani Alias *et al.*, 2023) Other than cholinesterase inhibitors, its antioxidant properties would also help in inhibiting the symptoms of Alzheimer's disease, as oxidative stress is one of the contributing

factors for this disease. Taxaxerol and taxaxerone are present in the roots of plant. The bark of roots contains resin, tannin, starch and flavonol glycosides. The root nodule contains glycine, alanine, valine, leucine, α -aminobutyric acid, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, arginine, ornithine, histadine, γ -aminobutyric acid.

Seeds

The seed contains bitter acid resin as an active principle with fixed oil, tannic acid and glucose, also contains a cotyledon, which is full of granular starch and bitter in taste. There are two chemicals which are isolated from seeds viz. Sitosterol and anthoxanthin. Other than that seed-oil yields palmitic, stearic, oleic, linoleic and linolenic acids. Oils from blue and white-flower varieties have been found to have almost similar composition. Seeds also contain cinnamic acid, hexacosanol, nucleoprotein with its amino acid sequence somewhat similar to insulin. Recent studies indicate that seed extracts can neutralize reactive oxygen species and inhibit digestive enzymes, suggesting their utility in functional food and pharmaceutical applications (Padmanabhan & Parvatam, 2022, as cited in Prasad *et al.*, 2025)

4. Pharmacological activities of *Clitoria ternatea*

The bioactivity profile of *Clitoria ternatea* is driven by its diverse bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, anthocyanins, and cyclotides (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2008; Srichaikul, 2018). These constituents support a wide range of therapeutic effects, from indigenous medical systems to advanced neuroprotective therapies.

Trichogenic (Hair Growth) Activities

Aside from its systemic effects, *C. ternatea* also shows strong potential in dermatological applications, particularly in enhancing hair density. The rich presence of anthocyanins boosts blood flow to the scalp by dilating small capillaries, helping sustain healthy follicle function. Scientific evidence indicates that this effect is due to their ability to induce vasodilation and improve circulation. Enhanced circulation ensures better delivery of oxygen and nutrients to the hair follicles, which is crucial for strengthening hair roots, reducing hair fall, and promoting the anagen (growth) phase of the hair cycle (Isara *et al.*, 2025; Sharnarhi *et al.*, 2025). Research indicates that flower extracts can be more effective than synthetic minoxidil in initiating hair growth, strengthening the hair shaft, and reducing premature graying through antioxidant protection.

Neurocognitive and Memory-Enhancing Activities

Historically regarded as a brain tonic in Ayurveda, *C. ternatea* is scientifically recognized for its ability to improve "neurocognitive" functions—the ability to think, reason, and process information. The plant contains alkaloids and triterpenoids that influence the central cholinergic system (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2008). Ethanolic and aqueous extracts have been shown to significantly improve learning and memory in rat models by

enhancing cholinergic activity in the hippocampus and cortex (Taranalli & Cheeramkuzhy, 2000). Additionally, aqueous root extracts have been found to stimulate dendritic branching in hippocampal CA3 pyramidal neurons, which play a critical role in memory formation and consolidation (Rai *et al.*, 2002; Kalita *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, high phenolic and flavonoid content in the flowers provides strong antioxidant activity that neutralizes free radicals, protecting neurons from oxidative stress-induced cognitive decline (Srichaikul, 2018).

Anti-Alzheimer's Effects

C. ternatea targets the core pathologies of Alzheimer's disease, specifically the depletion of acetylcholine and cellular damage. In addition root extracts inhibit acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE), preventing the breakdown of acetylcholine and potentially improving symptoms of memory loss and learning impairment (Alias *et al.*, 2023) and also by the presence of threonine and histidine in aerial and root extracts supports hippocampal acetylcholine levels (Kalita *et al.*, 2024). In zebrafish models, treatment with *C. ternatea* has been shown to increase the number of Purkinje cells and improve the structure of Oligodendrocytes (responsible for myelin sheaths) damaged by aluminum chloride exposure (Ramli *et al.*, 2022).

General Systemic Activities

Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic

The anti-inflammatory activity of *C. ternatea* is mainly due to its ability to regulate immune responses at the molecular level. In addition to alleviating neuroinflammation, its flavonoids and polyphenols suppress the production of key pro-inflammatory enzymes, particularly COX-2 and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS). Extracts reduce neuroinflammation and localized pain, which contributes to overall cognitive and physical health (Lijon *et al.*, 2017).

Antidiabetic and Antipyretic Activities

Recent pharmacological studies have clarified the plant's role in metabolic control. Its antidiabetic effect is mainly attributed to the dual inhibition of α -amylase and α -glucosidase, enzymes responsible for breaking down complex carbohydrates into glucose. By slowing carbohydrate digestion, *Clitoria ternatea* helps reduce postprandial blood glucose levels and decreases pancreatic workload. In addition, its antipyretic activity acts on the hypothalamic thermoregulatory center, promoting peripheral vasodilation and heat loss. This mechanism supports its traditional use as a natural alternative to synthetic fever-reducing drugs such as paracetamol (Chusak *et al.*, 2018; Mukherjee *et al.*, 2008).

Sedative and Anxiolytic Activities

The effects of *Clitoria ternatea* on the central nervous system are dose-dependent and mechanism-specific. At

lower doses, it may enhance cognitive function, whereas higher doses, particularly via intraperitoneal administration—activate the GABAergic pathway. By potentiating the inhibitory action of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), neuronal excitability is reduced, resulting in sedation and muscle relaxation.

5. DISCUSSION AND LIMITATIONS

Overall, existing studies on *Clitoria ternatea* highlight its rich phytochemical composition and wide range of biological activities. It contains important bioactive compounds such as anthocyanins (especially ternatins), flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and phenolic acids (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2008; Oguis *et al.*, 2019) which are mainly responsible for its pharmacological effects. These constituents have been linked to strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, neuroprotective, and anticancer properties. In particular, its high anthocyanin content contributes to effective free radical scavenging, while other secondary metabolites influence various biological processes and pathways.

However, most of the current evidence is based on *in vitro* studies and *in vivo* animal the direct application of these findings to clinical use is still limited.

Moreover, there is significant inconsistency in research methods, including differences in extraction techniques, plant parts used, solvent types, and dosage formulations. This lack of standardization makes it challenging to compare results across studies and to establish reliable conclusions about its therapeutic potential. Environmental factors such as location, soil conditions, and cultivation practices may also influence the phytochemical content of the plant, affecting the consistency and reproducibility of results.

Principal limitation in the current literature is the absence of well-designed human clinical trials that can properly evaluate safety, effectiveness, and appropriate dosage. Without these studies, translating preclinical results into evidence-based medical applications remains uncertain. Only studies published in English-language journals were included, which may limit the breadth of available research. Additionally, there may be publication bias, where studies with positive results are more likely to be published. While the review offers a broad overview, it does not provide a detailed quantitative analysis or meta-analysis of the findings, which may limit the ability to draw precise conclusions about the efficacy of specific phytochemicals or biological activities.

Clitoria ternatea shows strong potential as a natural source of bioactive compounds with multiple biological activities, these findings should still be interpreted cautiously. Future research should prioritize and well-structured clinical trials to fully confirm its therapeutic value and ensure its safe use in pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, and functional food applications.

6. Future research

Future research should aim to further explore and enhance the understanding of *Clitoria ternatea*, particularly its phytochemical composition and wide range of biological activities, by addressing existing gaps in the current literature, especially those related to limited *in vivo* studies and human clinical trials. In addition, future studies should focus on the comprehensive identification and quantification of its key bioactive compounds, such as anthocyanins (ternatins), flavonoids, saponins, and other phenolic constituents, as well as the standardization of extraction and isolation techniques to ensure consistency and reliability of results. These gaps remain largely unaddressed due to the limitations of existing studies and addressing these limitations will help strengthen the scientific basis for the medicinal and industrial applications of *Clitoria ternatea*.

7. CONCLUSION

Clitoria ternatea is a perennial herb from the Fabaceae family found in tropical and subtropical regions. It is a highly important medicinal plant known for its rich phytochemical composition and wide range of biological activities. The plant contains numerous bioactive compounds, particularly anthocyanins such as ternatins, along with flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and other phenolic compounds, which contribute significantly to its pharmacological properties. These phytochemicals are responsible for its strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, neuroprotective, and anticancer activities.

The high concentration of anthocyanins, especially ternatins, not only gives the flowers their distinctive blue coloration but also enhances their biological efficacy as natural antioxidants and free radical scavengers. These properties support its traditional use in herbal medicine and explain its increasing applications in cosmetics, nutraceuticals, and functional food products. Overall, *Clitoria ternatea* demonstrates strong potential as a natural therapeutic agent due to its diverse phytochemical profile and biological activities; however, further scientific studies are still necessary to fully confirm its clinical effectiveness and safety, these investigations are essential to establish consistent therapeutic outcomes, determine optimal formulations, and ensure its safe application in pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, and functional food development.

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